

Recommended citation: Evans, R. A., Liang, G., & Tucker-Kulesza, S. E. (2018). Researching Undergraduate Women Who Thrive in Engineering Student Project Teams. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 764-771). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672693.

Researching Undergraduate Women Who Thrive in Engineering Student Project Teams

R. A. Evans

Director, Engineering Communications Program
Cornell University
Montour Falls, New York USA
rae27@cornell.edu

G. Liang

Assistant Professor, Educational Leadership
Kansas State University
Manhattan, Kansas USA
wq09jamor@gmail.com

S. E. Tucker-Kulesza

Assistant Professor, Civil Engineering
Kansas State University
Manhattan, Kansas USA
sekulesza@ksu.edu

Conference Key Areas: Innovative Teaching and Learning, Gender and Diversity in Engineering Education, Curriculum Development

Keywords: Gender, Inclusion, Engineering Education

Introduction

In “Women in Engineering: A Review of the 2014 Literature,” Peter Meiksins et al., echo the “familiar explanations for why there are relatively few women in US engineering” [1]. Those explanations fall into three categories: 1) childhood socialization, arguing that engineering is generally perceived by children as a “male field;” 2) the lack of support for female students in engineering programs, leading young women to “opt for majors other than engineering;” and 3) the recognition that often women engineers “do not always thrive or remain in the field after they enter the workplace.” These are fairly common explanations. No one offers a satisfactory explanation and all are related to the “pipeline metaphor,” still the dominant frame for policy and research [2]. More telling is that the current literature has focused almost exclusively on the negative – why are female children *not* interested in engineering, why do young women *not* enroll or stay in engineering majors, and why do professional women engineers *not* thrive? What if, in addition to focusing on the negative, certainly important, we also focused on the positive – why are female children attracted to engineering, why do young women stay in engineering, and why do professional women engineers thrive?

In a college of engineering at a university located in the northeastern region of the US, participation in extra-curricular undergraduate engineering student project teams (ESPTs) has grown steadily. Students from that university’s seven undergraduate colleges/schools are represented, as are all fourteen engineering majors in the college. In the academic year 2016-2017, there were twenty-four ESPTs totaling

slightly more than one thousand students. And, at the same time that aggregate student participation has been increasing, the number of women students participating has also increased. In the academic year 2008-2009, only 15.5% of those participating in ESPTs were women. Compare that to 42.7% in 2016-2017. In addition, the number of women in positions of leadership has increased dramatically across the teams.

There are generally three types of ESPTs: 1) those associated with competitions, e.g., Baja (Society of Automotive Engineers), Steel Bridge Team, Violet Satellite Project; 2) those associated with service, e.g., Engineering World Health (EWH), Engineers without Borders (EWB), Engineers for a Sustainable World (ESW), and 3) those teams who are performing for a particular “client” e.g., App Development and Data Science. For participating students, ESPTs provide them with an opportunity to engage in real engineering work that is similar to professional practice and supplementary to their regular academic courses [3].

Investigating the positive for women in this context will allow us to explore the qualities/features that facilitate the positive, as well as how those qualities/features get realized through the specific practices. This leads us to our two research questions: What can we learn from these women’s experiences relevant to and in ESPTs? and How that might help us to better understand the positive and how might that better understanding help us to design more rewarding and enduring engineering educational experiences, curricula and identities for women (and men)? We follow with a description a description of our research methodology and then present a single case study in order to highlight the common themes and offer a predominant narrative story.

Method

Using a feminist, activist interpretive lens, we are interested in “a particular view that builds on and from women’s experiences,” giving voice to those “hidden women” and encouraging an “emancipatory praxis” [4]. Such a perspective is often referred to as standpoint epistemology. This research is a collection of case studies, involving “a number of cases jointly in order to inquire into a phenomenon, population or general condition” [5]. The data collection methods include interviews and photovoice, photographs and videos, which not only encourage participants to share their experience, but also provide researchers the opportunity to make sense of that experience as if they were present.

1.1 A Feminist, Activist Interpretive Lens and Standpoint Epistemology

Standpoint epistemology “argues that all knowledge is constructed from a particular position” [6]. As this epistemology frames this study, we are interested in the positive experiences in the everyday lives of these women as those experiences are related to their participation in ESPTs. We understand that the meaning of positive is always particular and partial and that what is particular and partial about that meaning is solely determined by those women participants. We also understand that while we may expect commonalities, these positive experiences will not only differ among the participants, but that in our role as researchers we need to account for our own standpoints. We need to build and maintain “dialogues across these differences” in order to “stay connected” and perhaps, more importantly, to acknowledge our own biases in our attempts to re-present those experiences [6]. Finally, we understand that also in our role as researchers (and as activists) we should support these women naming and claiming their positive experiences.

1.2 A Multiple Case Study

Case study methodology focuses on a specific and distinct “phenomenon of scientific interest” [7]. Our focus on a group of individuals has led to a multiple case study of which a “critical case” sampling strategy was used [8]. The selection criteria include: 1) undergraduate women who participate in ESPTs for at least 2-3 years; 2) participants who consider themselves to have positive experiences; and 3) participants who are willing to share those experiences. Further, we intentionally attempted to include women from all three types of ESPTs and, if possible, in leadership positions – an indicator of thriving beyond just surviving.

1.3 Interviews and Photovoice

For recruitment, we sent an email describing the study to all the women participating in ESPTs. Meetings were arranged with 10 volunteers that were forthcoming and, during those meetings; the study was explained in more detail. Also, prior to actually contacting possible volunteers, we consulted with the Institutional Review Board (IRB) to make sure that we were adhering to all Institutional Review Board (IRB) protocols.

We conducted three semi-structured interviews: life history [9], learning journey [10] and photovoice [11]. The life history interviews allowed us to attend to the ways these undergraduate women in engineering narrated their lives. Learning journey interviews encourage the interviewee to “reflect on events and be able to relate to learning aspects” [10]. Finally, we employed a “form of participatory action research,” photovoice, which “places participants behind camera lenses,” encouraging them “to document elements of their lives [in project teams] within their own terms” [11]. Participants were then asked to assign meaning to those photographs and videos.

All the interviews were transcribed and coded [8]. We employed, variously named, open or topical or descriptive coding. We made a list of all emerging themes, then grouped the themes to eliminate redundancy, and discussed any differences or disagreements among the coders. A theme passage was used to create a conceptual map – a visual representation of our findings. The last step in the coding process was to write a single narrative story that captures the experience of these women.

Results

The thematic passage of this research is shown below.

Agency is the originating and continuing motivation for these young women to participate in ESPTs. They understand that agency is only realized when they are confronted with **challenging** problems, participate in “hands-on” **doing** in response, and produce “tangible” **outcomes**. Through ESPTs and **engineering praxis**, then, they discover new ways to experience, indeed, to express agency - to solve problems, do hands-on things, and produce important outcomes. Through their continuing involvement, they experience **community** or the shared sense of responsibility to self, others, project and team emergent from their engineering praxis. They understand both **failure** and **commitment** as opportunity and necessity, respectively, and that both are critical to realizing agency. Finally, as they engage with ESPTs and in engineering praxis, they experience a powerfully rich and authentic identity, they experience **becoming an engineer**.

Nickie (a pseudonym) is a member of an upper middleclass family with two parents (neither of whom are engineers), one sister and two brothers. She was born in the northeastern part of the US. She differentiated herself from the other members of her family, “I was probably the least athletic person ever, so I had to find other things...” She enjoyed reading, writing and drawing. “I became very artistic ... and “was super curious” about space, ancient Egypt. She characterized her childhood by saying, “I grew up with Barbie dolls and ballet.”

According to Nickie, high “school became part of my identity.” And perhaps because she was attending an all-girl Catholic school – “very antiquated ... very traditional ... a lot of history” – where the arts, writing and philosophy were very important; she felt that she was on a “liberal arts track ... [with] every single intention of becoming an English major.” Still when she took a physics course as a freshman, “it kind of blew my mind how much you could do with it.” She also “did really enjoy science.” Nickie recalled two experiences that show the importance of the experience of agency as that experience was related to science. The first experience happened in middle school in a “tech class.”

I had this solar car. It was a piece of plastic PVC with two wheels and a little solar servo. But, I made sure that I had the cleanest axle and I want[ed] zero friction as I'm going down. No one else in this class cared at all. But they tested all the times for the whole eighth grade, and my group got the fastest time, and I was like “Oh, Wow.”

The second experience happened in that first freshman physics course.

I remember we had this one lab ... where you had to do calculations and use kinematics and roll a marble and hit another marble that was on the floor. I took this really seriously. And, I was the only one in the class to get my marble to exactly hit that [other] marble I was so happy. I was like “Wow, this is so cool.”

For Nickie, “just doing something precise and getting something from it was great.” The importance of the experience of agency appeared in all of the initial life story interviews, though there were clearly differences in the particular circumstances, agency always seemed to involve three components: challenge, doing and outcomes.

Challenge involved solving problems, problems not unlike realizing near zero friction or rolling a marble in just such a way to hit another. Nickie described an early experience on her high school debate team that was a “total embarrassment.”

Instead of doing what freshmen usually do, presenting the oratory of others, Nickie decided to do what seniors do – original oratory. Her description of the results were “It was awful.” Her response was to scale back and practice. In her junior year, she attempted original oratory again and this time found success, “When I finally was better ... I felt like “I can public speak ... that’s awesome.” For these women, their early challenges were “hard.” The challenges very often required going “very against the grain” or involved defying general societal and peer expectations.

Doing or participating in something “hands-on,” “making something,” “tinkering” was also important. Throughout her high school, Nickie had been thinking of her future. She asked herself, “What do I want to spend the rest of my life doing?” and her answer was “I want to invent, I want to make.” She recalled her first visit to the campus of the university she would eventually choose:

... I'm doing a tour, and one of the big things they were pushing is project teams ... that was the deciding factor for me. I kind of saw how much hands-on experience these kids were getting, and it blew my mind that an undergraduate – someone that would be me in a year or three years from now – was building a plane that flew by itself. I couldn't fathom that.

Apart from the solar car and the marble roll, Nickie did not have many “hands-on experiences” before university. Still, she along with others recalled that, “I kind of had this idea that I wanted to do something ... really, really technically difficult.” However, among these women, there was recurring and personal component to this doing. Nickie said, for example, “I feel that I'm always trying to prove myself ... trying to prove myself to myself, that I can do it.” For all of these women proving to themselves and others that they could do something difficult was “validation.”

Agency also involves outcomes. When Nickie was considering possible career paths, she asked herself “What's going to have the most impact?” Her answer was STEM. She says, “I was just so incredibly attracted to the idea of making something ... of having a final product.” Her rationale was “... what is what I am doing, at the end of the day, going to give back ... otherwise what is the point of doing it?” For Nickie, as for the other young women, outcomes that are tangible and yield a final product were important. Whether it was the fastest time with a solar car or hitting a marble or proving to yourself and others that you could “public speak,” the result mattered. Nickie spoke about her interest in space, “I want us to go to Mars.” She continues, “I think of the last docking with the ISS, they sent up so many medicines, and they had these cool crystalized vaccines that can only grow in microgravity. That's cool.” Give back, real impact – otherwise what's the point.

Nickie is someone who valued agency long before she knew anything about engineering. For her, the components of the experience of agency found (and continue to find) an opportunity for expression in ESPTs. She says,

I started on ... Mars Rover the second week of my freshmen year. So really my whole entire college experience had been defined by the team ... if I think back to a specific time, I think back about what was going on in the team, that defines that time period, which kind of says how much of [an] influence the team has had.

When Nickie recounted her ESPT learning experience, there were many stories of agency. Those stories showed her addressing challenging problems:

So my junior year ... we actually did a redesign, we changed the whole suspension system ... we changed all of our system geometries, cut all the masses ... and a big mass to cut had to come out of the wheels ... we went from about 4 pounds per [wheel] to about 1.7 pounds per.

Those stories showed her doing hands-on work:

So we ended up spending the semester doing an iterate analysis of these wheels ... which was really exciting ... I think there was some nights that I just pulled all-nighters just plugging little numbers into the ANSYS program and running it.

And, those stories showed her realizing tangible results:

So we had this whole design [for wheels that could be 3-D printed and] I remember calling every person who printed this material ... and finally we found this [company]

who makes this material ... so they said 'If you give us your design and we can put it on display, then we will give it to you [print the wheels] for free.' Okay Fantastic.

However, ESPTs offered more just a way to express/experience agency. They offered community. Nickie very much respected the other students that she worked with, "the people that I have been able to work with over the years ... just really inspiring, really incredible." She also received respect in return. As part of a routine review, she was told "You know what you are talking about. Talk about it and have some confidence in yourself." This shared respect does not mean that there weren't serious confrontations. Indeed, Nickie recalled one incident during her first year:

The way we had made our parts ... some of our holes were a little bit off on this one square bracket that was ... connecting the whole E-core to the camera mast[So when they went to] "put it on ... my friend and I got this text from our team lead ... I think I still have it Like the subtitle was "THIS IS A DISGRACE." I think that 10 or 11 that night we ran to the lab, I was in my pajamas ... Freaking out, like we need to fix it all."

When I asked her how she responded to that confrontation and others that she has experienced, she said, "I think that I really wanted to be those people ... [in them] I saw what I could be." While there was and is support in ESPTs, some of the recurring qualities associated with community and those relationships were demand and responsibility – the expectation that participants will successfully complete their tasks and respond specifically to team needs.

There were two more qualities/features of these women's experience that recurred during the learning journey interviews: failure and commitment. In the women's descriptions of their ESPT experiences, failure was constant, but (and this is important) never final. Nickie recounted failure in practice, "our holes were a little bit off on this square bracket," an example of technical failure; "our motors weren't working," a situational and unanticipated failure; "we had this whole design ... and we ended up losing ... our funding to make these wheels," a personal failure." Nickie once asked a mentor on the team "What does it take to be a leader? Do you think that I have the potential?" Her mentor's response was "No. You ask too many questions and you don't know the answers." Finally, there was even failure at competitions, "... at competition we ended up not competing in a whole category which is a whole hundred points because we had micro-controller issues. For Nickie and for the other women, these ESPT experiences of failure became opportunities to respond – to get better at "CADing," to "redesign the motors," to find an alternative way, someone else "who makes this material," to realize "Wow, I do need to know the answers" or to raise her own standards. Each year's failure for the Mars Rover team offered an opportunity to "redesign the rover" anew. Failure was an important part of engineering praxis – it defined the challenge, directed the doing and engendered better outcomes.

The other recurring feature/quality was commitment. Over and over again, the women participating in ESPTs told me of the hours and hours and hours that they spent involved in their ESPT. Nickie refers to the Mars Rover team as a "prevalent burden." She along with the other women "didn't have weekends because we just test all weekend long. I also didn't have that much time after school because we would just go back to the lab." However commitment involved more than just time. Before her first competition, Nickie had fallen ill, "I had a 104 fever for four straight

days ... [and] had to postpone my flight ... I should have gone to the hospital." Still, "I ended up going to the competition. I still had a fever, pretty sick. But, I couldn't miss competition ... I wouldn't have missed it for anything." Commitment also involved more than just time and dedication. It also involved making a contribution. Nickie says of her fellow team members, "many were very, very intense, difficult, almost impossible to please. Like you wouldn't get a compliment even if you did something really well ... [but] once you got a compliment, you were like, 'Wow. Okay I actually did something really well.'" ESPTs require time, dedication and contribution.

For participating women students ESPTs offer many important experiences roughly correspondent to those of professional engineering practice. Students learn how to generate a production schedule, to adhere to a budget, to raise funds, to design and test and redesign intricate technological equipment. They also provide students, specifically these women, with the experience of becoming an engineer. Nickie like the other women was not an engineer when she began in her ESPT. Yet, she had models, peers who she could learn from, who were "inspiring, really incredible." These models were so influential that Nickie "wanted to meet them where they were ... wanted them to accept me as someone worthy." She "wanted to be those people ... I saw what I could be." And what could Nickie be? She could be someone who understood and appreciated the intricacies of the design process – identifying "variables," devising ways to "test these variables," learning how "to optimize." She could be someone who understood and appreciated the importance of "decision matrices" and "a plan." Finally she understood and appreciated the importance of "deliverables," determining if she and her team "are going to have a good product." For Nickie, however, becoming an engineer involved more. It involved "learning how to actually confront people ... having a backbone ... being able to standby something." It involved "learning how to trust people ... [and how] trusting them gives them ownership." In a brief summary she says,

"Wow, I can go on for days. I have learned a lot of technical things ... those have really helped me in my internships and probably landed me some jobs. But the interpersonal skills, the leadership skills that I would have never ... there's no reason I would have ever learned them in a classroom setting ... [the] team is ... more ... because I'm never not thinking about it ... it's that project team way of life."

Conclusion

Through our telling of Nickie's story, revealing the results of our research through a single case study, we have tried to answer our research questions: To learn about the qualities/ features of these women's experiences relevant to and in ESPTs and how those positive experiences might help us to design more rewarding and enduring engineering education experiences, curricula and identities for women (and men). We believe that the answers to both questions are contained in our thematic passage. Foremost, we should foster experiences of agency that are realized through challenges, opportunities for hands-on doing, and actual outcomes. All elements should become progressively more demanding and require a deeper and broader understanding of engineering praxis – one that is only possible if we encourage the development of an enduring community or communities. It is through their continued participation in these communities, responding to the demands and fulfilling their responsibilities that they experience a range of models for ways to become and be engineers. We must encourage failure as opportunity, rather than as a somewhat catastrophic and/or final event. We need to require commitment – ask that they give

their time and dedicate themselves to making a contribution. Finally, we need to provide occasions for them to reflect and become aware of their own becoming. This may have been the most powerful experience that Engineering Students Project Teams (ESPTs) offer to students. The data indicated that this was an important reason why these women thrived. A final note: Not one of the ten women interviewed encountered an ESPT environment free of sexist attitudes and/or behaviors. Some of the environments were less overtly sexist. Others were more overtly sexist. However, what **empowered** these women in those environments are the above qualities/features of their experiences in ESPTs. In one way or another, these women were empowered to respond in a way that transformed that environment, despite the pervasiveness of sexism.

REFERENCES

- [1] Meiksins, P. et. al., (2017), *A compendium of the SWE annual literature reviews on women in engineering: 16 years of analysis and insight from the SWE magazine*. <https://research.swe.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/SWE-Lit-Review-Compilation-2017.pdf>
- [2] Lichtenstein, G. et. al., (2014). Retention and persistence of women and minorities along the engineering pathway in the United States. In Aditya Johri & Barbara M. Olds (Eds.) *Cambridge handbook of engineering education research* (pp. 601-632). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- [3] Foor C. E, et. al., (2013) "You choose between TEAM A, good grades, and a girlfriend – you get to choose two!" How a culture of exclusion is constructed and maintained in an engineering design competition team. *Proceedings of the 120th Annual American Society of Engineering Education (ASEE) Conference*, Atlanta, GA.
- [4] Olesen, V. (1998) Feminisms and models of qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds). *Handbook of qualitative research*. (pp. 158-174) Sage Publications, Inc. Thousand Oaks, CA.
- [5] Stake, R. E (1998) Qualitative case studies. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds). *Strategies of qualitative inquiry*. (pp. 119-149) Sage Publications, Inc. Thousand Oaks, CA.
- [6] Sprague, J. (2016) *Feminist methodologies for critical researchers: Bridging differences*. Rowman & Littlefield. New York, NY. USA.
- [7] George, A. L. & Bennett, A. (2005) *Case studies and theory development in the social sciences*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
- [8] Creswell, J. W. (2016) *30 essential skills for the qualitative researcher*. Sage Publications, Inc. Thousand Oaks, CA.
- [9] Goodson, I & Sikes, P. ((2009) *Life history research in educational settings: learning from lives*. Open University Press. New York, NY.
- [10] Adriansen, H. K. (2012) Timeline interviews: A tool for conducting life history research. *Qualitative Studies*, Vol. 3, No.1, pp. 40-55.
- [11] Latz, A. (2017) *Photovoice research in education and beyond: A practical guide from theory to exhibition*. Routledge. New York, NY.